

THE ROLE OF PLANTS IN HUMAN LIFE AND CLEANING THE ATMOSPHERE

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.7245867>

ELSEVIER

Gaybullayeva Mashhura Fakhritdinovna

*Teacher of the Bukhara Institute
of Natural Resources Management*

Received: 22-10-2022

Accepted: 22-10-2022

Published: 22-10-2022

Abstract: Plants play a very important role in human life, we cannot imagine our life without plants. 90% of the products we consume are obtained from plants, besides, they enrich the atmospheric air with oxygen. It is also a nutritious food for livestock. The ears of grain-bearing plants are food for caterpillars. Understanding the role of plants in our lives, each of us sho Plants, air, animal husbandry, farm, vegetables, poly crops.uld contribute to the growth of plants.

Keywords: Bessel operator, Gursa problem, classical solution, singular coefficient,

About: FARS Publishers has been established with the aim of spreading quality scientific information to the research community throughout the universe. Open Access process eliminates the barriers associated with the older publication models, thus matching up with the rapidity of the twenty-first century.

The place of plants in human life is very important. Since most of the world around us is made up of plants, we should have complete information about plants. For example, bread products, fruits and vegetables, wood products, oils, fodder for livestock, agricultural soaps, additives used in perfumes, in short, thousands of examples can be given.

We can use plants again as scenery. Quality clothes are made from the fibers of some plants. We can use cotton as an example, because cotton has been grown in Uzbekistan since ancient times, exported to foreign countries where the demand for its fiber is very high, and it has had a very good effect on the development of Uzbekistan.

In our farm, attention is very much needed in livestock and poultry farming, of course, plants are nutritious food for livestock, and grain of spiked plants is nutritious food in poultry farming, as it can be seen that we cannot imagine our life without plants. .

As our honorable president Shavkat Miromonovich said, we should make good use of every inch of our land, we should plant vegetables, fruit trees, decorative trees, and flowers. If every family grows even a few such plants, firstly, we will prevent poverty and secondly, laziness, and the land will not be wasted. Even if it is small, we can get additional income, at least we can grow products for ourselves, which in turn will bring profit, savings and benefit to the family. Now, another important issue is that plants play a big role in cleaning the atmosphere for us. They release oxygen and absorb carbon dioxide. We know that oxygen is very necessary for humans and animals.

The more oxygen there is in our air, the more it is useful for our health, for example: in mountains or mountain forests, because of the dense vegetation, they are considered places rich in oxygen. Even if we go to mountainous areas or sparsely populated resorts, we will notice a good change in our health for a long time. We must contribute to the growth of trees. We know from a young age that the motherland begins with the family. If everyone starts greening from his family, we would not be indifferent to his family and his homeland, the ecological condition of our homeland, the health and culture of ourselves and the next generation. .

Based on the conditions of the city of Bukhara, we should increase ornamental trees and flowers around the roads and in the city. Trees add to the beauty of the city, clean the air and help to cool down in the heat of the summer. We know well the climatic conditions of Bukhara, taking into account the salinity level, we should pay attention to the breeding of plants that are resistant to salt and can quickly adapt. The result would be good if everyone would consciously make a small contribution and make this issue a tradition at home or at the place of work.

We would achieve a good result if everyone had the knowledge and skills to grow and develop plants in their spare time, and if we could attract and interest our youth from a young age, they would certainly spend their free time in vain. , due to idleness, we will make our young people to increase their love for family, motherland, nature and plants, even if they spend useful time on work instead of spending time on useful work.

Plants not only clean the air, but decorative plants raise the mood of a person and give inspiration to a person to work with pleasure or creativity. Seeing the miracle that nature has gifted us, our eyes are happy, we feel uplifted, and we would explain the useful aspects of plants to the younger generation and increase their interest. From annual plants to perennial plants, we need to understand that all of them release oxygen, and their usefulness from the root to the fruit.

For example, in the house where we live or in the office where we work, if there are simple flowers or trees in general, a person's mood rises, when a person is in a good mood, his work productivity is high and it shows the height of our culture. This shows how cultured, tasteful, and high our ethics and aesthetics are.

Summary: So, knowing that plants have a very important place in human life, we can first of all give children the right understanding about plants from their youth, make them feel the importance of us in our lives, and create love in their hearts. I think we will achieve a result. Children who love nature, for example, will never run over the flowers on the side of the road or break the branches of the trees. When he goes to the market, there is a boy who brings one flower.

As they say, there will be a lake, the result will be good if everyone contributes at least one plant. The preparation of medicinal plants in medicine also increases our love for plants.

Every person should live the life that is given to us not only, but also very beautifully. For this reason, the role of plants is extremely important for humans. Sweet fruits, various products, home furnishings, various perfumes, cleaning agents for our cleanliness, quality wooden products for our modern homes are also obtained from plants. There are many others that have not been mentioned, so each of us should contribute to the preservation and reproduction of the plants that nature has gifted.

FOYDALANILGAN ADABIYOTLAR:

1. Mirziyoyev Sh.M O'zbekiston Respublikasini rivojlantirishning beshta ustivor yo'nalishi xarakterlar strategiyasi Toshkent, O'zbekiston, 2017, 48b
2. Turapov I, X.Namozov. "Tuproqshunoslik xaritalari agrokimyoviy kartagrammalarni tuzish va foydalanish" ,"meliorativ tuproqshunoslik" Toshkent, 2006.
3. Baxodirov, P. Uzoqov. Tuproqshunoslik. Toshkent "Mehnat" Nashriyoti. 1995.507
4. Karimov. E.Q. F.SH. Xudoyberdiyev. Tuproqshunoslik va dehqonchilik asoslari. " Durdona" nashriyoti , Buxoro. 2019 213 bet.
5. G'aybullayeva, M. F., Muxamadov, Q. M., & Bobojonov, S. (2021). O 'ZBEKISTON TUPROQLARINING MIKRO-VA MAKROAGREGATLIGI. Интернаука, (21-5), 68-69.
6. Egamova, D.A, Shukurova N.O, Ahmadov B.O (2020). EFFICIENT AND RATIONAL USE OF LAND RESOURCES IS A REQUIREMENT OF THE TIME. In Эффективность применения инновационных технологий и техники в сельском и водном хозяйстве (pp. 327-328).
7. Egamova, Dilchehra Adizovna; Bobojonov, Said; Muhamadov, Qamariddin Muxtarovich. "BUXORO VILOYATIDA TUPROQ MELIORATIV HOLATINI YAXSHILASH CHORA-TADBIRLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH." Студенческий вестник 18-11 (2021): 92-94
8. Tukhtaeva K. T., Egamova D. A. CHARACTERISTICS OF DESERT-SANDY SOILS OF KANIMEKH DISTRICT //The Way of Science. – 2014. – С. 49.
9. Жураев Т. Х., Эгамова Д. А. ГЕОМЕТРИЧЕСКОЕ МОДЕЛИРОВАНИЕ ДЛЯ СИМУЛЯЦИИ ТЕХНОЛОГИЧЕСКОГО ПРОЦЕССА ОБОРАЧИВАНИЯ ПЛАСТА //СОВРЕМЕННЫЕ ИНСТРУМЕНТАЛЬНЫЕ СИСТЕМЫ, ИНФОРМАЦИОННЫЕ ТЕХНОЛОГИИ И ИННОВАЦИИ. – 2020. – С. 106-109.

10. Egamova Dilcheyra Adizovna, Bobojonov Said Utkirovich, & Mukhamadov Kamariddin Mukhtarovich. (2021). IMPROVEMENT OF SOIL RECLAMATION (ON THE EXAMPLE OF BUKHARA REGION). *Euro-Asia Conferences*, 5(1), 285–286.

11. 11.Egamova, D. A., Azimova, S. J., Мухамадов, Q. M., & Bobojonov, S. (2021). LABOR RELATIONS ON THE FARM. *Актуальные научные исследования в современном мире*, (6-2), 23-26.

12. 12.Tuxtayeva, X. T., Egamova, D. A., & Hamroyeva, B. Z. (2022). The Potential of Ecotourism in the Economic and Social Development of Bukhara Region. *Zien Journal of Social Sciences and Humanities*, 8, 155-158.

13. 13.Adizovna, E. D., & Farrukhovna, Q. L. (2022). LAND RESOURCES MANAGEMENT ISSUES. *European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies*, 2(05), 138-141.

14. 14.Adizovna, E. D. (2022). ECONOMIC AND ECOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF AGRICULTURAL LAND PROTECTION IN INTER-FARM LAND CREATION. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 3(5), 1304-1310.
Adizovna, E. D. (2022). ECONOMIC AND ECOLOGICAL ASPECTS OF AGRICULTURAL LAND PROTECTION IN INTER-FARM LAND CREATION. *Web of Scientist: International Scientific Research Journal*, 3(5), 1304-1310.

15. 15.Adizovna, E. D., & Shokirovich, H. S. (2022). Features of Land Monitoring in Agriculture. *American Journal of Social and Humanitarian Research*, 3(6), 193-196.